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ECONOMIC MODELLING OF SCALING NETWORK EDUCATIONAL STRUCTURES BASED ON FRANCHISING WITHOUT INVOLVING PUBLIC FUNDING

**JEL Classification: I21, L14, L26, D23, M13
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Annotation. The relevance of the study is determined by the growing demand for alternative models of educational development under conditions of limited public funding, increasing competition in the education services market, and the expanding role of private initiatives. In this context, franchising is considered a promising mechanism for scaling networked educational structures; however, its effective implementation requires solid economic justification that takes into account network effects, financial risks, and quality assurance of educational services.

The purpose of the article is to substantiate economically viable approaches to scaling networked educational structures based on franchising models in the absence of public funding, ensuring their financial sustainability and effective development.

Research methods are based on the application of institutional and systems approaches, methods of economic analysis and generalization, comparative analysis of franchising models, as well as analytical modeling of efficiency and financial sustainability indicators of networked educational structures.

Results of the study. The economic and institutional prerequisites for the functioning of educational franchises without state support have been examined. The mechanisms of economic growth and scaling in the context of network effects formation and income distribution among participants have been characterized. A system of key economic indicators for assessing the efficiency and financial sustainability of networked educational structures has been established. The main problems of scaling related to quality control of educational services, institutional heterogeneity of the regulatory environment, and financial risks have been identified.

Conclusions. It has been proven that scaling networked educational structures based on franchising is economically viable provided that growth rates are aligned with self-financing capacities, quality of educational services is maintained, and effective contractual coordination is ensured. The feasibility of phased network expansion, integration of economic and quality indicators into management systems, and the use of flexible financial mechanisms has been substantiated.

Prospects for further research are associated with the development of formalized economic and mathematical models for scaling educational franchises, as well as with empirical analysis of the impact of digital platforms and data analytics on improving financial sustainability and educational outcomes in networked structures.

Key words: networked education systems, economic sustainability, network effects, private investment, contractual coordination, financial autonomy.

Анотація. Актуальність дослідження зумовлена зростанням попиту на альтернативні моделі розвитку освіти в умовах обмеженого державного фінансування, посилення конкуренції на ринку освітніх послуг та розширення ролі приватних ініціатив. У цьому контексті франчайзинг розглядається як перспективний механізм масштабування мережевих освітніх структур, однак його ефективне впровадження вимагає економічного обґрунтування, що враховує мережеві ефекти, фінансові ризики та забезпечення якості освітніх послуг. Метою статті є обґрунтування економічно доцільних підходів до масштабування мережевих освітніх структур на основі франчайзингових моделей за відсутності державного фінансування, що забезпечують їхню фінансову стійкість та ефективний розвиток. Методи дослідження базуються на застосуванні інституційних та системних підходів, методів економічного аналізу та узагальнення, порівняльного аналізу франчайзингових моделей, а також аналітичного моделювання показників ефективності й фінансової стійкості мережевих освітніх структур. У статті розглянуто економічні та інституційні передумови функціонування освітніх франшиз без державної підтримки. Схарактеризовано механізми економічного зростання й масштабування в контексті формування мережевих ефектів та розподілу доходів між учасниками. Визначено основні проблеми масштабування, пов'язані з контролем якості освітніх послуг, інституційною неоднорідністю регуляторного середовища та фінансовими ризиками. Підсумовано, що масштабування мережевих освітніх структур на основі франчайзингу є економічно доцільним за умови, що темпи зростання відповідають можливостям самофінансування, підтримується якість освітніх послуг та забезпечується ефективна договірна координація. Обґрунтовано доцільність поетапного розширення мережі, інтеграції економічних та якісних показників у системи управління, а також використання гнучких фінансових механізмів. Перспективи подальших досліджень пов'язані з розробкою формалізованих економічних і математичних моделей масштабування освітніх франшиз, а також з емпіричним аналізом впливу цифрових платформ і аналітики даних на поліпшення фінансової стійкості та освітніх результатів у мережевих структурах.

Ключові слова: мережева організація освіти, економічна стійкість, мережеві ефекти, приватні інвестиції, контрактна координація, фінансова автономія.

Introduction

The scaling of networked educational structures based on franchising models without the involvement of public funding brings to the forefront the problem of forming economically sustainable mechanisms for educational development under conditions of limited budgetary resources and increasing competition in the educational services market. Traditional institutional approaches to the expansion of educational institutions are largely oriented toward state support, which constrains their adaptability, innovativeness, and speed of scaling. At the same time, franchising as a form of network organization of educational activity requires scientifically grounded economic models capable of explaining patterns of growth, risk distribution, and value creation among network participants in the absence of budgetary funding.

The issue of economic modeling of such structures is directly related to key scholarly challenges in the contemporary economics of education, particularly the development of network organization theory, institutional economics, and entrepreneurial models for the provision of socially significant services. The insufficient development of quantitative and analytical tools for assessing the effects of scaling educational franchises complicates the forecasting of financial sustainability, quality management effectiveness, and long term viability of such systems. In practical terms, this creates obstacles to informed managerial decision making regarding the expansion of educational networks, the attraction of private investment, and the provision of accessible and competitive educational services without reliance on state subsidies.

An analysis of scholarly research indicates the gradual formation of an interdisciplinary research field that integrates approaches from human capital economics, social entrepreneurship, and organizational design. In particular, A. Ilina demonstrates that investments in human capital have a cumulative effect on economic and social development, forming a foundation for decentralized models of scaling education, including through franchising networks [1].

In the context of organizational and economic scaling mechanisms, K. Zajko et al. demonstrate that social franchising enables the replication of organizational and knowledge resources while minimizing marginal growth costs, which is fundamentally important for educational networks that do not rely on public funding [2]. Using the example of the international Impact Hub network, A. Giudici et al. substantiate that the economic success of scaling franchising structures depends on combining the standardization of core processes with the preservation of local unit autonomy, which makes it possible to sustain innovation capacity and the financial viability of the network [3]. At the same time, A. DeSantola emphasizes that the expansion of franchising networks is accompanied by increasing control and coordination costs, which should be formally incorporated into economic scaling models [4].

The universality of the franchising model as a scaling instrument is confirmed by I. Alon et al., who simultaneously stress the need to adapt financial and contractual mechanisms to sector-specific conditions, particularly in education [5]. J. Asemota and T. Chahine consider social franchising as an alternative to grant-based and budgetary funding models, highlighting its capacity to ensure long-term financial autonomy for socially oriented organizations [6]. In the educational sector, K. Juusola and L. Rensimer identify structural tensions between the commercial interests of franchisees and the educational mission, which generates additional economic risks for transnational educational franchises [7].

Issues of organizational effectiveness in educational franchising are examined by M. Gonzales and M. Roberts, who view franchised schools as an alternative model of educational organization capable of achieving economies of scale and the unification of managerial decisions [8]. At the same time, K. Karmeni et al. demonstrate that excessive rigidity of control within franchising systems can constrain innovative processes, which constitutes a critical limitation for educational structures oriented toward development and quality [9]. An entrepreneurial education model within franchising that integrates instructional, marketing, and behavioral components, thereby enhancing the economic performance of educational franchises, is proposed by S. Quach et al. [10].

The factors of effectiveness in social franchising are synthesized by D. Cumberland and B. Litalien, who identify financial self sufficiency, knowledge management, and internal coordination as key conditions for the sustainable scaling of networks [11]. Social franchising as a form of entrepreneurship that makes it possible to combine economic feasibility with social impact without the involvement of public resources is examined by M. Ziółkowska [12]. The importance of internal network development mechanisms is emphasized by C. Domínguez Falcón et al., who demonstrate that systematic staff training functions as an instrument of internal marketing and a factor of financial stability in franchising structures [13]. M. Van Lunenburg et al. show that the scaling of social and sustainable initiatives is possible only in the presence of organizational models capable of self replication, economic autonomy, and the accumulation of human capital [14].

Despite the substantial body of literature, economic mechanisms for scaling networked educational structures based on franchising without state funding remain insufficiently explored in scholarly research. The impact of network effects on the financial sustainability of educational franchises, the relationship between economic indicators and the quality of educational services, as well as long term financial risks and the effectiveness of revenue distribution models among network participants have been examined only to a limited extent. This article systematizes the economic and institutional prerequisites for the functioning of educational franchises, уточнено механізми масштабування з урахуванням мережевих ефектів, identifies key indicators of financial sustainability, and formulates recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of the development of networked educational structures without the involvement of public funding.

The aim of this article is to determine economically justified approaches to scaling network-based educational structures through franchising in the absence of public funding, ensuring their financial sustainability and effective development. To achieve this aim, the following objectives have been formulated:

- 1) to analyze the economic and institutional conditions for scaling network-based educational structures through franchising without public funding;
- 2) to identify the mechanisms of economic growth in educational franchises and the system of indicators for evaluating their effectiveness and financial sustainability;
- 3) to reveal the main challenges in scaling network-based educational structures and to substantiate recommendations for enhancing its effectiveness in the absence of public funding.

Results

The economic prerequisites and institutional foundations for the functioning of network-based educational structures that develop through franchising without public support are determined by market competition, growing demand for applied and flexible educational services, and limited budgetary resources. In this context, mechanisms of self-financing, contractual coordination, and standardization of educational activities acquire significant importance, as they ensure alignment of the entrepreneurial motivation of network participants with requirements for quality and legitimacy of the educational process. The institutional architecture of educational franchising is based on the contractual distribution of rights, obligations, and risks between the franchisor and franchisee, which allows maintaining control over scaling processes without involving public funds (Table 1).

Table 1

Economic prerequisites and institutional foundations for the functioning of networked educational structures based on franchising without state support

Group of factors	Content of economic and institutional conditions	Significance for the functioning of the network
Market conditions	Solvent demand, competition between private education providers	Stimulation of quality improvement and adaptation of educational products
Financial prerequisites	Self-financing, franchise fees, royalties, private investment	Ensuring the scalability and financial stability of the network
Institutional and legal environment	Licensing, accreditation, franchise agreements	Legitimization of activities and reduction of regulatory risks
Organizational standardization	Unified programs, methodologies, brand, and management procedures	Maintaining consistent quality of educational services
Control and accountability	Audit, quality monitoring, financial reporting	Restriction of opportunistic behavior of participants

Source: compiled by the author based on [1, p. 75; 5, p. 48; 6, p. 2742; 11, p. 142]

In modern practice, these conditions are implemented through clearly structured franchising models, which are common in language school chains, IT academies, business education institutions, and private professional centers. The franchisor usually centralizes the development of training programs, performance evaluation systems, and marketing strategy, while the franchisee is responsible for local operational efficiency, personnel management, and interaction with end consumers. This division of functions reduces the transaction costs of scaling up while maintaining control over the quality of educational services across the entire network. Financial mechanisms, such as entry fees and royalties, serve not only a fiscal but also a disciplinary function in practice, encouraging franchisees to adhere to established standards and business models. Institutional requirements for licensing and accreditation in this context are a tool for filtering

market participants and increasing consumer confidence, especially in the segments of supplementary and informal education [11, p. 142]. As a result, the combination of market incentives, contractual coordination, and regulatory restrictions creates a practically effective model for scaling networked educational structures, capable of ensuring sustainable growth without relying on public funding.

Economic growth and the scaling of educational franchises are driven by the formation of network effects, whereby an increase in the number of participants increases the value of the educational product and the efficiency of the entire network. In franchised educational structures, these processes are based on a combination of a common brand, centralized services, and agreed financial mechanisms that ensure the alignment of the economic interests of the franchisor and franchisee and create conditions for sustainable scaling (Table 2).

Table 2

Mechanisms of economic growth and scaling of educational franchises in the context of network effects and income distribution

Mechanism	Economic content	Role in franchise scaling
Network brand	Cumulative growth in trust and recognition	Acceleration of entry into new markets
Economies of scale	Reduction in average costs through centralization of functions	Increased network profitability
Platform integration	Shared digital learning and management solutions	Enhanced manageability and transparency
Revenue sharing	Royalties and other payments between participants	Balance of incentives and development funding
Knowledge accumulation effect	Collective learning and exchange of practices	Acceleration of innovation and quality improvement

Source: compiled by the author based on [2; 3, p. 296; 4, p. 101; 10, p. 121; 14, p. 1018]

The growth in the number of franchise outlets directly strengthens the brand, which reduces the individual costs of each franchisee for attracting students and shortens the payback period. In language school or IT academy chains, this manifests itself in the fact that new branches immediately gain access to the established reputation and stable demand that has been accumulated by the entire chain [14, p. 1018]. The centralization of support functions, such as marketing, educational content development, and digital platforms, provides economies of scale that are virtually unattainable for autonomous educational institutions. For example, the use of a single learning platform makes it possible to replicate courses at minimal marginal cost while simultaneously implementing analytics of student performance across the entire network. This creates a basis for data-driven quality management and the adjustment of educational programs in line with actual learning outcomes. The financial distribution of income within the franchise plays a system-building role, as royalties serve as a source of investment in brand development, program updates, and innovation. In practice, effective networks use differentiated royalty models that take into account market size, the stage of development of the franchisee, and its financial results [3, p. 296]. At the same time, there is a mechanism for accumulating organizational knowledge, whereby the successful practices of individual franchisees are integrated into the general standards of the network, strengthening its competitive position. The combined effect of these mechanisms ensures the sustainable economic growth of educational franchises and makes scaling not a linear expansion, but a process of cumulative improvement in the efficiency of the entire network.

Assessing the performance and financial stability of networked educational structures in the scaling process requires the use of a system of economic indicators that can reflect not only current financial results but also the network's long-term ability to reproduce and grow. At the stage of network expansion, it is particularly important to align the operational performance indicators of individual franchise units with

the aggregate indicators of the entire network, which allows for the identification of imbalances between the pace of scaling and financial capabilities. In this context, the main economic indicators should reflect profitability, liquidity, investment attractiveness, and the network's ability to adapt to growth without losing financial stability (Table 3).

Table 3

Key economic indicators for assessing the effectiveness and financial stability of networked educational structures in the scaling process

Indicator	Economic meaning	Analytical significance for scaling
Operating margin	Ratio of operating profit to revenue	Assessment of the effectiveness of the network's core activities
Average revenue per location	Revenue generated by a single franchisee	Identification of network unit productivity
Financial autonomy ratio	Share of equity in the overall financing structure	Assessment of the financial independence of the network
Payback period	Time to recoup funds invested in scaling	Analysis of the investment feasibility of expansion
Growth rate of total revenue	Dynamics of total network revenue	Characteristics of economic growth stability

Source: compiled by the author based on [3, p. 302; 5, p. 57; 8, p. 43; 9, p. 1494; 12, p. 43]

The application of a system of economic indicators in the process of scaling network-based educational structures makes it possible to move from fragmented financial control to an integrated assessment of the sustainability of the entire network. In this context, operating margin serves as an indicator of an educational franchise's ability to convert growth in activity volumes into financial outcomes without a proportional increase in costs [9, p. 1494]. Its dynamics reflect the effectiveness of managerial decisions related to the centralization of functions, the digitalization of the educational process, and the optimization of administrative expenditures in line with network expansion.

The indicator of average revenue per franchise unit is used to assess the internal balance of the network and the degree of business model replicability. Its stability indicates consistency in educational standards, pricing policy, and marketing approaches, whereas significant differentiation among units signals uneven adaptation of the model to local markets or variations in the quality of local management. In networks of vocational and continuing education, this indicator often serves as a basis for adjusting program formats and cost structures [9, p. 1494].

The financial autonomy of a network-based structure becomes particularly important under conditions of rapid scaling, as it reflects the system's ability to finance development without excessive reliance on external resources. High values of this coefficient correlate with increased resilience to demand fluctuations and a reduction in systemic risks, which is critical for educational franchises with long training cycles. The investment payback period, accordingly, serves as a tool for assessing the effectiveness of initial investments and is widely applied in the development of standard financial models for the entry of new participants into the network.

The growth rate of total revenues should be interpreted not as an independent objective but as the outcome of the interaction among other performance indicators. Its alignment with profitability and financial autonomy indicates a controlled pattern of expansion, whereas an imbalance among these indicators points to the risk of extensive growth without a solid economic foundation. Thus, the system of key economic indicators provides an analytical basis for decision making on the pace and direction of scaling network-based educational structures, combining the assessment of current efficiency with the forecasting of long-term financial sustainability.

The scaling of network-based educational structures through franchising is accompanied by a complex set of scientific and practical challenges arising from the combination of educational specificity and the entrepreneurial logic of development. One of the key problems is ensuring consistent quality of educational services during rapid network expansion, since the standardization of educational programs and procedures does not always guarantee an equivalent level of pedagogical expertise, staff motivation, and compliance with methodological requirements across different franchised units [8, p. 44]. This situation increases the risk of a formal replication of the educational product without adequate alignment with the declared learning outcomes.

A significant constraint is the institutional heterogeneity of the educational environment, particularly differences in regulatory requirements, licensing procedures, and accreditation frameworks, which complicate the unification of network operations and increase the transaction costs of scaling. An additional challenge is the legal uncertainty surrounding the status of nonformal and supplementary education, which negatively affects opportunities for strategic planning and investment attraction in the development of educational franchising. In this context, the franchisor is compelled to combine strict control standards with adaptation to local institutional conditions, a balance that is not always economically efficient.

Financial risks of scaling manifest themselves in the growing dependence of the network on the stability of franchisee cash flows, financial information asymmetry, and the potential instability of royalty models in cases of uneven unit development. Excessively rapid expansion may lead to margin erosion, increased coordination and controlling costs, and the emergence of systemic risks, whereby the financial difficulties of individual franchisees are transmitted to the reputation and revenues of the entire network. A distinct challenge is the limited capacity of traditional financial indicators to capture in a timely manner the latent risks associated with the quality of the educational process and long-term consumer loyalty.

From a scholarly perspective, the issue of formalizing the relationship between economic indicators of scaling and qualitative educational outcomes remains insufficiently developed, which complicates the construction of adequate management models for franchised educational networks [5, p. 57]. The absence of established methodologies for the integrated assessment of quality, institutional compliance, and financial sustainability reduces the effectiveness of managerial decision-making and limits the potential for the sustainable development of networked educational structures operating under a franchising model.

The effectiveness of scaling such networks without public funding can be enhanced through the comprehensive application of economic, organizational, and institutional measures aimed at ensuring long-term sustainability. Of particular importance is the strengthening of centralized quality management through the implementation of unified digital platforms for monitoring learning outcomes, pedagogical performance, and learner satisfaction, which makes it possible to reduce the risk of deterioration in educational quality during rapid network expansion.

The effectiveness of scaling can be enhanced through flexible financial architecture of franchising models, which provides for differentiated conditions of entry fees and royalties, taking into account the development stage of the franchise unit and local market potential. This approach creates economic incentives for attracting new participants without excessive financial burden while simultaneously ensuring stable funding sources for developing network infrastructure, updating educational programs, and supporting the brand.

The reduction of institutional and financial risks is facilitated by the formation of transparent and formalized contractual mechanisms of interaction between franchisor and franchisee that clearly define standards of educational services, responsibilities of the parties, and control procedures. Of particular importance is the integration of economic indicators with indicators of educational outcomes quality into the management analysis system, which allows making decisions regarding scaling rates based on comprehensive evaluation rather than exclusively financial criteria.

Also advisable is the phased nature of network expansion with preliminary testing of the business model in pilot markets and adjustment of standards based on the results obtained. This approach reduces

the probability of systemic errors and increases the adaptability of the franchising model to various socio-economic conditions. Collectively, the implementation of these recommendations forms a practical foundation for controlled and economically justified scaling of network-based educational structures capable of functioning and developing without involving public funding.

Conclusions. The study finds that scaling network-based educational structures through franchising without public funding is economically viable provided that network effects, contractual coordination, and financially sound governance mechanisms are properly aligned. It is demonstrated that the effectiveness of this model is determined not by the pace of network expansion but by the ability to ensure cumulative growth of economic value, maintain the quality of educational services, and preserve financial sustainability. The main challenges of scaling are identified as the risk of declining educational quality, institutional heterogeneity of regulatory environments, information asymmetry among network participants, and the limited availability of integrated tools for assessing economic and educational outcomes. It is emphasized that the dominance of extensive growth strategies leads to erosion of margins and the accumulation of systemic financial risks. The feasibility of implementing recommendations aimed at strengthening centralized quality management, developing a flexible financial architecture of franchising relationships, formalizing contractual mechanisms, and pursuing phased network scaling is substantiated.

Future research prospects are associated with the development of economic and mathematical models that capture the relationship between financial and quality parameters in the development of educational franchises, as well as with empirical analysis of the impact of digital platforms on reducing scaling risks.

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